

Building Group Cohesion

Authors

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Title	Learning to cooperate building group cohesion
Stage (s)	Primary and/or Secondary Education
Subject	Physical Education
Basic goal	Learn to be together, to be able to work together (Fernandez-Rio, 2016)

Lesson 1. Presentation

Main goals:

- *Know each other better.
- *Work with as many different classmates as possible during each activity.

Activities:

- ***My funny name:** sitting in a circle, each person in the group introduces himself/herself by saying his/her name using a “funny” tone of voice. The next student presents this partner imitating the “tone” and presents “himself/herself with a “funny” tone too. The same continues until the last person in class.
- ***It “itches” here:** sitting in a circle, one person introduces himself: “My name is Carlos and it itches here (scratching the body part he/she mentioned)”; the next person says: “his name is Carlos and it itches here (scratching Carlo’s body part) and my name is Maria and it itches here (scratching her body part)”.

Note:

It is very important that all students change partners as many times as possible in each activity.

<p>The game continues with the next person in the circle. The students have to say the specific name of the body part (knee, elbow, hand...).</p> <p>*Truth and Lie: in pairs, one student tells the other 3 things about him/herself: 1 of them is a lie and the other 2 are true; the other student tries to guess which is the lie (the first one tells him/her). Then, the students change roles. When everyone has finished, they all return to the central circle to introduce the partner, saying his/her name and telling only the things that are true about him/her.</p> <p>*Name throw: in a circle, the students must pass the ball to a partner calling his/her name; if the passer does not know it, he/she asks the receiver and then throws the ball; several balls will be included, and the only rule is that each student can only pass once to the same classmate. After a few minutes, the game starts again, but this time the person who receives the ball also has to say the name of the person who threw the ball to him/her (if he/she does not know, he/she asks that classmate).</p> <p>Debrief: a whole class assembly, led by the teacher, is held at the end of the lesson; the key elements will be reviewed and the students can express how they felt, what difficulties they had and what good experiences they take away from the session (help from a classmate, overcome a personal fear or embarrassment, etc.).</p>	
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Lesson 2. Icebreaking

<p>Main goal: *Get comfortable working with all classmates.</p> <p>Activities: *Colours: students walk around the gym and decide on one colour: red or blue. On the clap, they pair with the closest classmate, count to two and say loud the colour each one chose at the same time. If they</p>	<p>Notes Again, it is very important that all students change partners as many times as possible in each activity.</p> <p>Also, it is very important that students treat each other well while performing the tasks.</p>
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match, they give each other a hug, if not they shake hands and continue walking. The same action is repeated, changing partners.

***Part by part:** the teacher says: “with your right hand, touch something ‘colour red’ on a classmate”. He continues: “without letting go, with your left hand touch something ‘colour yellow’ on a classmate. And again: “without letting go, with your left foot touch something ‘colour white’ in a classmate. And again: “without letting go, with your era touch something dark in a classmate”.

***Eye connection:** all students stand in a circle, no speaking allowed, arms to the sides touching other classmates’ arms. They all look at each other in the eyes. When two classmates “connect” (stare at each other for a couple of seconds), they switch places. They cannot “connect” again, and they must try to “connect” with other classmates. Students must learn to share turns and space.

***Lead the partner:** students in pairs, one holds the other by his/her hair (gently) and moves him/her around the gym. After a couple of minutes, they change roles. After a couple of more minutes, students find new partners and do the same, but this time they hold the classmate by the ear. The same activity can be repeated holding the partner by the arm, the neck....

Debrief: a whole class assembly, led by the teacher, is held at the end of the lesson; the key elements will be reviewed and the students can express how they felt, what difficulties they had and what good experiences they take away from the session (help from a classmate, overcome a personal fear or embarrassment, etc.).

Lesson 3. Trust one another

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Main goals:

- *Understand that it is good for you to cooperate with your classmates.
- *Feel that you can trust your classmates while working.

Activities:

***Equilibrium in twos:** the students pair up, facing each other: toe to toe and holding hands; without lifting the feet off the ground, both lean backwards keeping the body straight until they also stretch their arms; the couple must hold the position for 5 seconds to be successful; then, they find another classmate to do the same thing.

***Let yourself fall:** the students pair up, one behind the other; the one “behind” puts his/her hands on the shoulder blades of the one in front to make him/her feel “safe”. The other one leans back, keeping the legs and the body straight and the other stops and returns him/her to the initial position; they repeat the same action trying to lean a little bit more at each attempt, generating confidence in the partner. After a few attempts partners switch places. After a few minutes, students find new partners.

***Different parts moving:** groups of three students; they have to cross a 10-meter space fulfilling different “requirements” each time: a) only 3 feet can touch the floor; b) 5 different parts must touch the floor; c) 4 feet and two hands must touch the floor; d) some body parts must be at medium level and others at low level; g) all should move sideways and connected to each other.... and soon on.

***I faint, help me!!!:** each member of the class is given one of 4 colours: blue, red, white or green; they walk around the gym and the teacher calls out a colour; the students with this colour must shout: “I am going to faint”, to indicate their classmates that they must hold them so they do not fall to the floor.

Debrief: a whole class assembly, led by the teacher, is held at the end of the lesson; the key elements will be reviewed and the students can express how they felt, what difficulties they had and what good

Note

Again, it is very important that all students change partners as many times as possible in each activity.

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experiences they take away from the session (help from a classmate, overcome a personal fear or embarrassment, etc.).

Lesson 4. Know yourself

Main goal:

- *Place yourself in a difficult situation (blindfolded) and be successful.
- *Feel that your classmates will always help you.

Activities:

- ***Touch:** in pairs, one person holds one tennis ball on each hand facing upward; the partner, who is blinded, puts his/her hands on top of the tennis balls; the first one guides the blinded partner around the gym only through the tennis balls (very slowly at first); after a few minutes they switch places. After a few minutes, they change partners.
- ***Solitude:** the whole class is blindfolded; each student walks around the gym in silence; when he/she touches someone, they hold hands and continue walking; when one of them touches another person, he/she “let go” and join hands with the “new” partner; the students “join and separate” every time they touch someone. Students walk around with one arm up in front to protect feel safer. The teacher must bring back to the group those students that move away without noticing it.
- ***The bus:** the students make groups of four. Three are blindfolded and one can see; they line holding a pike in their right hand; the one that can see is last leading the group around the gym. After a few minutes, students rotate places.
- ***Beep Beep:** 4 students in the class are blindfolded and the rest of the group standing represents obstacles around the gym. The blindfolded students must reach the other end of the gym without crashing with the obstacles; when a blindfolded partner person approaches an obstacle, he/she makes a

Note

No joking allowed at any time.

constant 'beep-beep' noise for the blindfolded; the noise is louder or softer as the person is closer to the obstacle. After a few minutes, students change roles.

Debrief: a whole class assembly, led by the teacher, is held at the end of the lesson; the key elements will be reviewed and the students can express how they felt, what difficulties they had and what good experiences they take away from the session (help from a classmate, overcome a personal fear or embarrassment, etc.).

Lesson 5. Coop play

Main goal:

*Perform simple cooperative tasks to improve your cooperative skills.

Activities:

***Walk and share the space:** the goal for the whole class is to keep moving without touching anyone; at first, the class can move in half a basketball court, but every 30 seconds the space is reduced at half; the students must cooperate to share the space, keep moving and do not touch anyone.

***Ball in the air:** the students stand in a circle, with one in the middle with a ball; this one calls the name of a partner and throws the ball up in the air; he/she has to catch the ball before it hits the ground; then he/she repeats the action; the goal is to complete all the names without the ball touching the floor.

***Help anyone:** every student in the class puts a bean bag on his/her head; on the signal they have to move around the gym turning, jumping, climbing up and down obstacles...; if the bean bag drops to the floor, the student must stand still; a partner must take the bean bag and put it back on the partner's head without dropping his/hers; and soon.

Note

Simple tasks are used to debate how the students are working cooperatively.

***Obstacle course:** half of the class makes an obstacle with his/her body: crouching in a squatting position or standing with legs apart; on the signal, the other half of the class must jump over or go under the legs of their partners; the “obstacles” change to the “other position” every time someone passes over or under him/her.

Debrief: a whole class assembly, led by the teacher, is held at the end of the lesson; the key elements will be reviewed and the students can express how they felt, what difficulties they had and what good experiences they take away from the session (help from a classmate, overcome a personal fear or embarrassment, etc.).

Lesson 6. Collective score

Main goal:

*Keep working on class cohesion, building a cooperative learning atmosphere.

Activities:

***Collect them:** the equipment is spread all over; the class must collect everything and place it in a box before the end of the time set by the teacher. Ideas to improve the score are shared and the class tries a second time to do it better.

***Passing speed:** students stand in a circle; they have to pass a ball to the person in their right and try to beat the time. Ideas to improve the score are shared and the class tries a second time to do it better.

***Up in the air:** each student holds one balloon; on the bip, everyone throws his/her balloon up in the air; the goal is to keep all the balloons in the air; the time stops when the first one touches the floor; Ideas to improve the score are shared and the class tries a second time to do it better.

Note

This simple technique can help students grow strong as a group.

<p>*Filling the basket: half of the class stands on one end of the gym with two balls per student and the other half on the other end; on the bip, the first ones throw the balls to other half of the class; if a ball is caught in the air, it is placed in a basket, if not, it is send back to the other end; the time is stopped when all the balls are in the basket; Ideas to improve the score are shared and the class tries a second time to do it better.</p> <p>Debrief: a whole class assembly, led by the teacher, is held at the end of the lesson; the key elements will be reviewed and the students can express how they felt, what difficulties they had and what good experiences they take away from the session (help from a classmate, overcome a personal fear or embarrassment, etc.).</p>	
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Assessment rubric			
	4 - EXCELENT	3 - SATISFACTORY	2 - NEEDS IMPROVEMENT
Collaboration	Always listens, shares and supports others' efforts. Seeks to unite the team by working collaboratively with everyone	Generally, he/she listens, shares and supports others' efforts. Does not cause problems in the group	Sometimes shares and supports others' efforts; sometimes is not a good member of the group and causes problems
Contribution	Always try to provide helpful ideas	Almost always, he/she tries to provide useful ideas	Only sometimes, he/she tries to provide useful ideas
Attention	Stays focused on the task that needs to be done and upon completion is attentive to support his peers	Most of the time, he/she stays focused on the task and upon completion tries to support his/her peers	Only sometimes, he/she stays focused on the task that needs to be done and upon completion supports his/her peers

References

Fernandez-Rio, J. (2016). Implementing Cooperative Learning: A Proposal. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 87(5), 5-6.
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